

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

Pediatric psychooncology

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Abstract:

Pediatric psychooncology is multidisciplinary specialty focusing on emotional, social, behavioral, ethical and spiritual aspects of children and young adults with cancer and their families. Managing childhood cancer care is a complex process and requires dealing with issues that are not present in cancer care of adults. Pediatric practice ranges from babies and toddlers through primary school age children to adolescents. It is essential to understand that these are not lumped together and that the young patients must be treated in age appropriate ways, according to their developmental phase.

Leading associations for pediatric oncology, adopted evidence-based standards for pediatric psychooncology care. Pediatric patients should routinely be subjected to systematic assessments of their psychosocial health care needs and have access to psychosocial support programs. The cancer treatment is psychologically demanding for family members as well. Parents are confronted with different fears, feelings of helplessness, guilt, sadness and /or anger, while healthy siblings often remain in the shadow of a sick child.

Good communication means good patient care. Pediatric radiotherapy requires specific knowledge and skills which include confidence in dealing with children in the context of their families and cancer treatment. The child and the family should be fully informed and prepared for the procedure before it begins. Honest and open explanation about treatment procedures and acknowledgment of child's fears and concerns are essential to reduce psychological distress.

Trained psychologist should be an indispensable member of a multidisciplinary team, across the cancer treatment trajectory.

Key words: pediatric psychooncology, distress, radiotherapy

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